

EFEKTIVITAS PEMBELAJARAN DARING BAGI GURU MADRASAH IBTIDAIYAH DI MASA PANDEMI COVID-19

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian adalah untuk menganalisis efektivitas pembelajaran daring bagi guru madrasah ibtidaiyah (MI) se-Kota Magelang. Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah deskriptif kualitatif. Sumber data dan informasi utama diperoleh dari subjek penelitian dengan populasi sebanyak 31 orang yang terdiri dari 29 guru dan 2 kepala madrasah. Teknik pengumpulan data menggunakan observasi, dokumentasi, wawancara, dan angket. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian disimpulkan bahwa: pembelajaran daring di MI se-Kota Magelang selama masa pandemi COVID-19 berjalan secara “efektif”; guru telah menjalankan pembelajaran daring saat pandemi COVID-19; guru dapat menguasai “*smartphone*” dan “*laptop*” sebagai *tool* dalam pembelajaran daring; “WhatsApp” merupakan pilihan utama sebagai media dalam melaksanakan pembelajaran daring; dan guru “setuju” jika pembelajaran daring dilanjutkan dengan memperhatikan rencana pelaksanaan pembelajaran daring (RPPD) yang telah dibuat sesuai dengan indikator yang telah terukur sesuai dengan capaian pembelajaran.

Kata Kunci: analisis efektivitas; COVID-19; guru MI; pembelajaran daring.

Abstract

The research aimed to analyze the effectiveness of online learning for madrasah ibtidaiyah (MI) teachers throughout Magelang City. The research method used descriptive qualitative. The main sources of data and information were obtained from research subjects with a population of 31 people consisting of 29 teachers and 2 madrasah principals. Data collection techniques used observation, documentation, interviews, and questionnaires. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis. Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that: online learning at MI in Magelang City during the COVID-19 pandemic was running "effectively"; teachers have been running online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic; teachers can master "smartphones" and "laptops" as tools in online learning; "WhatsApp" is the main choice as a medium in carrying out online learning; the teacher "agrees" if online learning is continued by paying attention to the online learning implementation plan (RPPD) that has been made in accordance with indicators that have been measured in accordance with learning outcomes.

Keywords: effectiveness analysis; COVID-19; MI teacher; online learning.